

German basic research, classification, and training in glove prints

Matthias Braune ^{1 2}

¹ Kriminaltechnisches Institut im
Landeskriminalamt Bremen, In der Vahr 76,
28329 Bremen, Germany
(engl.: Forensic Science Institute at the
State Criminal Police Office of Bremen)

² FSB - Forensisches Sachverständigenbüro
Braune, Malenter Str.8a, 28844 Weyhe,
Germany
(engl.: Forensic Expert Office Braune)

Correspondence

FSB - Forensisches Sachverständigenbüro
Braune, Dipl.-Ing. [FH] Dipl.-Verww. [FH]
Matthias Braune, Malenter Str.8a, 28844
Weyhe, Germany
E-Mail: mail@german-forensics.de

Funding information

FSB - Forensisches Sachverständigenbüro
Braune

Abstract

The processing of glove prints still does not occupy the place it deserves in forensic practice. The extreme decline in dactyloscopy prints in criminal cases due to the wearing of gloves has not been compensated for decades. More than half of all criminals in Germany now wear gloves when committing crimes, but when criminals are apprehended, gloves are rarely seized, nor are glove prints secured in sufficient quantities at the relevant crime scenes. This is partly because many police officers are unaware that gloves in most cases have individual surfaces and can be directly linked to traces at the crime scene. On the other hand, forensic investigators are often unable to interpret glove prints during many operations and may confuse them with weather-induced structures. All coated gloves (including dot-patterned gloves), smooth and suede leather gloves, multi-surface gloves, and even disposable gloves can be identified. This article aims to highlight the basic possibilities of glove prints and to identify common types of gloves. In addition, there is an overview of the training program for forensic experts specializing in glove prints in Germany.

KEYWORDS

glove prints, handprints, fingerprints, shoe prints, dactyloscopy, forensic investigation, securing evidence, technical form traces

Introduction

The first glove print comparisons were documented in Germany as early as 1925, and their forensic use was described in detail in 1952 by Florentino Santamaria Beltran in the International Criminal Police Review and in 1956 by Arne Svensson and Otto Wendel in their book 'Tatortuntersuchung' (Crime Scene Investigation). These early works focused mainly on the criminalistic comparison between leather gloves and the prints they left behind. At that time, leather was still considered an individual material, and this remained unchanged until the publications by German forensic scientists Marquardt, Kurras, and Schill in 1987 and British dactyloscopist Gerald Lambourne in 1988. At that time, leather, textile, disposable, and household gloves were the main types available, and, as in Prussian times, they were used during criminal acts to avoid leaving dactyloscopy traces or for self-protection against possible injury.

Fig. 1: Criminals wear gloves when committing crimes

Although German glove manufacturer 'Reusch' launched the first latex foam glove with an additional studded structure in 1973, designed as a goalkeeper glove for the German national soccer team, it was not until the 1990s that the glove market exploded and more and more different types of gloves became available to consumers. For example, various textiles with varying coatings were mixed. The manufacturing processes of manufacturers Profas (now UVEX-Safety), Roeckl, Fitzner, W&R, Hase, Leipold, Münch, WERO, KCL, MAPA, SHOWA, Towa, MCR, Magid, United Glove, etc. for leisure, work, and chemical protection gloves became increasingly precise and extensive. Global players in the disposable glove sector emerged, such as Ansell, Top Glove, Hartalega, Nastah, Kossan, Honeywell, and Kimberly-Clark. In short, from this point on, there were gloves for every occasion.

In 1986, DNA analysis was used for the first time to solve crimes, and from that date onwards, there was another reason for criminals to wear gloves when committing crimes. As a result, fewer and fewer dactyloscopy prints have been found at crime scenes to date. Today's surveillance camera recordings show that many more perpetrators wear gloves at crime scenes and hardly ever "work" with their bare hands. However, the number of glove prints found at crime scenes has not increased proportionally, even though it should be more than twice as high as the number of papillary line prints. Why is that?

The explanation for this is actually quite simple: most police investigators are unaware that the majority of gloves have surface structures that are just as unique as fingerprints and can be matched to a trace at the

crime scene to the same extent. In addition, many forensic investigators are unable to recognize glove prints, which means that they are not secured at the crime scene.

Since 2005, the State Criminal Police Office of Bremen has been conducting intensive research on gloves and the traces they leave behind. At that time, the central forensic training program in Germany was restructured, and as part of the Bremen-led project to redesign the field of shoe, tire, and glove print analysis, a training program specifically for glove prints should also be established. The new German expert training program was designed to be similar to a master's degree program and builds upon a bachelor's degree in engineering, as there was no comparable forensic training program at European universities and universities of applied sciences at the time—and there still isn't today.

The subject of shoe prints has been dealt with in depth since the 1930s in articles by German experts and later in international literature, such as the 1990 book “Footwear Impression Evidence” by William J. Bodziak. In 2005, there were also some good sources of literature on tire tracks that could be used for expert training. However, there was essentially no usable information regarding glove prints, apart from the previously mentioned limited evidence from old gloves. To change this situation, basic private research was initiated over the next six years at the Forensic Expert Office Braune in Weyhe (Lower Saxony) in cooperation with the State Criminal Police Office of Bremen.

Well over two thousand gloves of various types and models were purchased, and countless test series were conducted. In the process, methods for creating comparative prints were developed, or existing methods for securing fingerprints and shoe prints were further refined. Some methods are limited to specific types of gloves but are highly effective for those. Trade shows were attended (e.g., A+A International Trade Fair and Congress for Safe and Healthy Work in Düsseldorf), training sessions at glove manufacturers were participated in, and their production facilities were visited. Since many production facilities, particularly for disposable gloves, were and still are in Asia, correspondence had to be conducted with companies in Malaysia, China, Thailand, India, and Indonesia, and video footage of the production processes had to be obtained. A Malaysian company that works closely with the German firm CeramTec, which designs glove molds for Asia, even sent new and used dipping hands for disposable glove production. Contact with the Profas/UVEX expert and trained chemist Dr. rer. nat. Wolfgang Kesting, who served as head of Research & Development in the protective gloves division for decades.

In addition, various private German glove makers from the old guild were contacted; they provided extensive information on the manual production of gloves, documented individual work steps, and supplied leather samples for further testing (e.g., determining the pore structure and thus the type of leather).

A trained mechanical engineer does not know much about leather as a raw material, so German leather manufacturers had to be sought out and interviewed. In this context, leather finishing (e.g., re-pressing grain and split leather) and synthetic leather production played a particularly significant role. The same approach was taken with textiles (materials, yarn production, weaving and knitting processes, coating processes). A private spinning mill even contributed hair and yarn samples from non-European, exotic animals. Knowledge of sewing individual components also had to be acquired, as this can be highly significant when evaluating individual characteristics.

After reviewing all the information gathered from manufacturers and the physical samples, studying textile and leather science, and reading material on dactyloscopy and biology, work began on organizing all the information and dividing it into subcategories.

The types of gloves were divided into the following classes:

Fig. 2: Types of gloves

Possibilities for identifying the suspect

Depending on the type of glove, there are several basic approaches and investigation options in forensic practice:

- a. Characteristics of the glove surface or hand are visible in the trace (comparative examination by experts in technical form traces)
- b. DNA material adhering to the glove surface during the pre-crime phase is deposited in the glove trace (determination via DNA analysis)
- c. Fiber material from the glove is deposited in the trace (determination of the fibers)
- d. Papillary lines show through thin gloves and become visible in the glove trace (determined by dactyloscopy)

If a glove is secured that was left behind at the crime scene or on the escape path, etc., there are further possibilities:

- e. DNA material is deposited inside the glove when worn (determined by DNA analysis)
- f. With certain types of gloves, it is possible for papillary lines to show up inside the glove when worn. (Identification by dactyloscopy)

The following section focuses exclusively on alternative a). I will present the different types of gloves and briefly include my research findings in the explanations.

Textile gloves

These basically include knitted or mesh gloves as well as woven gloves. Knitted gloves are now manufactured seamlessly in a single step using different yarns on high-speed circular knitting machines. The other variant consists of cut-out individual parts made of knitted or textile fabric, which are then sewn together by hand using sewing machines on a piecework basis.

The product range of textile gloves extends from hand-knitted winter gloves and seamless textile liners to high-tech microfiber fine-knit gloves for sensory applications.

Despite the frequent presence of textile defects, it is very difficult to evaluate this type of glove print due to the usually poor and blurred print image or the superficial felting of this type of glove. However, it is not impossible to identify such a glove if there is a trace with distinctive textile features. On the other hand, it is almost impossible to identify fleece gloves, as the outer fibers resemble high pile felt, which, in my experience, makes comparison work utopian (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Examples of textile gloves

Coated or dipped textile gloves

As an extension of pure textile gloves, there are textile gloves that are coated to improve application-specific properties (e.g., grip, durability, safety). In addition to natural rubber coatings, there are also various synthetic coatings made of nitrile, PU, and PVC, or, for particularly chemically resistant glove types, coatings made of PVA, vinyl, butyl, fluorine, and chloroprene.

The prefabricated textile liners are usually placed manually on several hand molds and then immersed in a dip bath. Depending on the shape of the hand mold and the immersion depth, the gloves are partially or fully coated. In addition, different material thicknesses, dirt particles in the dip bath, dynamic influences, and drops create additional special features on the glove surface. For example, to improve the grip of the gloves, many manufacturers create so-called microporous or microstructured surfaces. These can be created by foaming materials, incorporating low-volume solids, or washable crystals, among other things. Various post-processing methods have become established, particularly for latex-coated gloves (blowing on the still-liquid latex film, chemical re-

dipping and creating a shrink-roughened surface, blowing on solid components, etc.). The coating effectively freezes the textile structure, which is particularly evident in thinly coated gloves. The different ways in which the glove is turned over the hand mold result in varying characteristics of the basic textile glove (e.g. widening of the knit structure in certain places) and ultimately also of the coated surface remaining at the end of production.

Each glove produced in this way has an individual surface structure, i.e., each of these gloves is unique after manufacture, and any marks produced can be quickly assigned to a specific glove if the image quality is good (Fig. 4). In the case of gloves with very thin coatings, wear often leads to wearer-dependent cracks in the coating, which in turn leads to the formation of further individual structures.

Fig. 4: Examples of coated or dipped textile gloves

Dotted gloves

The so-called “nubs” are partial coatings on a textile glove. When evaluating this type of glove, the manufacturing process used to produce the glove is a key factor, as there are two basic manufacturing processes for dotted gloves:

a) Nub screen printing

Gloves (usually knitted liners) are placed on a flat hand mold and passed under a screen-printing basin, where a nub structure is applied; these nubs usually have a particularly structured nub surface due to the way they are deposited on the textile surface.

b) Nub fabric printing

Application of a nub structure using the screen-printing process (roll or plate) to a textile web (usually fabric), which is later cut into individual pieces and sewn into a finished glove; these nubs are homogeneous and very flat and have a similar structure on their nub surface, which has a negative effect on individuality.

The advantage of this manufacturing method is the seams, where three surfaces with nubs sometimes overlap and meet at different intervals, creating an individual pattern.

Whereas in the past these were mostly so-called “round nubs” (which were sometimes difficult to distinguish from one another when determining a model), nowadays more and more special designs are being applied, e.g., company logos, lettering, figures, or nubs designed for specific uses. In stores, knobbed gloves are usually found among breathable gardening, work, grip, or leisure gloves (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Exemplary dotted gloves

Leather gloves

This traditional type of glove is basically divided into smooth leather and suede gloves. Genuine leather types can generally be easily distinguished by the different grain and pore patterns in the upper layer of leather. For over a century, the leather surface was considered unique, as the grain structures are known to have grown naturally and are therefore individual. However, leather manufacturers have increasingly turned to embossing inferior split leather (the split lower skin layer) to transform it into an apparently high-quality leather surface. In addition, upper leather strips are also pressed, for example, from cowhide into supposedly high-quality crocodile leather. Only an experienced forensic expert or leather specialist can uncover this deception based on certain identifying features. When pressed by rollers or plates, we obtain leather strips with identical surfaces and can no longer assume that each surface is unique. In my opinion, the previous principle that “leather is always unique” is therefore outdated. Experts are now required to carry out more detailed investigations into individuality. However, the synthetic leather material often used in glove production can be quickly identified by means of small tests, so that here too, no individual surface structure can be assumed.

Since genuine leather, pressed leather, and synthetic leather surfaces are sewn together from cut individual pieces to form a glove, there are distinguishable seams, folds, and adjacent surface areas at the surface transitions. This again explains the individual structure. The seams themselves, in conjunction with a repeating surface structure, also give the glove an individual character.

It should also be mentioned here that even traces of suede gloves can easily be assigned to a specific glove. The seemingly unstructured surface of suede has a unique structure. Experiments with short-pile suede gloves led to clear identifications and exclusions.

Fig. 6: Examples of leather gloves

Dipping hand mould gloves

This type of glove is divided into disposable gloves and so-called “multi-use gloves” (e.g., household and chemical gloves), both of which are manufactured using similar dipping processes.

During the manufacturing process, prefabricated dipping molds (usually ceramic replicas of hands, sometimes with arm parts, rarely steel or aluminum) are dipped in baths of liquid rubber, nitrile, or vinyl and then, after a few intermediate steps, they are cured. After vulcanization, the gloves are removed from the dipping mold hands by hand or blown off by machine. This means that the outside of the gloves is a negative impression of the surface of the dip mold. Based on my research, it can be assumed that the surfaces of the dip mold hands are unique, as after the hollow molds are produced by slip casting, a fine surface coating is applied to the molds, creating an individual surface structure.

Now, not only one glove is produced with such a mold, but thousands will be produced over the course of its service life. It was therefore previously assumed that there must be thousands of disposable gloves with identical surfaces. However, according to my findings, this is not the case. Since the dip molds repeatedly pass through a cleaning bath before actually being wetted with the glove material, the cleaning chemical ensures that the coating on the dip molds is chemically removed more and more with each cleaning bath, and the dip molds are thus subject to constant change. The change is gradual and has not yet been researched in sufficient detail, but it can be considered proven that this erosion occurs. A clear indication of this is that at some point the surface of the dip mold is so badly damaged that small pores have formed. If this is the case, a glove can no longer be separated from the dip mold without tearing. This is the point in production when a dip mold, or an entire set of dip molds, must be replaced with new models at the latest.

According to my information, between 50,000 and a maximum of 300,000 disposable gloves can be produced with one dip mold. In large factories, the molds are routinely replaced in batches (often every few months), checked again, and reworked if necessary.

Top-Glove from Malaysia alone sold approximately 70.3 billion disposable gloves in FY2025, with a production capacity of approximately 95 billion units in that year. Nitrile gloves traditionally account for approximately 75-80% of total production there (i.e., approximately 52-56 billion gloves). Considering the variability of gloves from a single mold in this production process, a maximum of 5,000 gloves with identical surfaces can occur worldwide. With a starting value of at least 52 billion gloves, a quick calculation shows that the theoretical probability of finding two gloves with the same surface during an investigation is 1 in 10.4 million. For comparison: DNA analyses indicate an extremely high degree of identity when $LR > 1$ billion.

This has a major impact on the evidential value of a print left with such gloves, contrary to previous assumptions. Although disposable gloves are still a mass-produced commodity, their individual character has increased many times over with the new findings.

A match between a print and a latex, nitrile, or vinyl glove is generally made based on the surface structure. However, disposable nitrile gloves undergo an additional surface change. Due to the usually very space-saving and tight packaging (e.g., packs of 100), various creases form in nitrile gloves, which are still visible in many places even when pulled onto the hand. These individual creases are also reflected in the prints made with these gloves and can be used for identification purposes. For some time now, textured nitrile gloves have been increasingly available in stores, which makes identification more difficult (see Fig. 7 / Image 3).

During investigations of glove prints made with vinyl gloves, it was noticed that the very soft and thin material often allows the papillary lines to show through, making additional dactyloscopy investigations possible. Our own experiments, conducted in collaboration with dactyloscopies in Bremen, led to the identification of the person who left the prints (see Fig. 7 / Image 4).

Fig. 7: Examples of single-use gloves

In addition to disposable gloves, there are also so-called “cleaning and household gloves,” as mentioned above. These are manufactured in a similar way to disposable gloves, except that the gloves are thicker due to multiple repeated dipping processes. The surface issue is the same. It is a little strange to see a strong burglar on a surveillance camera wearing pink household gloves while prying open a side door – but anything is possible to avoid leaving fingerprints at the scene of crime!

Household gloves usually have a better grip, which is achieved by the special profiling of the gripping surfaces. In addition, the surface structure is very resistant, which proves to be a disadvantage for forensic experts, as there are no changes in the profiling due to use and no formation of further individual structures. This also applies to the range of chemical protective gloves, which are produced using similar manufacturing methods or, in many places, by hand. However, other glove materials are used here, such as chloroprene, butyl, Viton, or fluorine rubbers, which may have different surface structures in detail (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8: Examples of household and chemical protective gloves

Multi-surface gloves

There are an increasing number of gloves on the market that have different surfaces on the palm, inside of the fingers, or back of the glove, some of which are sewn on or printed on. These surfaces are often made of leather, synthetic leather, embossed or molded plastics, or liquid-applied materials such as PVC or silicone. As the name suggests, the external appearance of these gloves consists of many areas, which are often found in critical areas, e.g., the fingertips, the base of the fingers, the base of the thumb, or the ball of the thumb.

When assessing the gloves, the expert must consider the manufacturing methods used for the individual surfaces, as their respective characteristics determine their individuality. The seams that are often present should not be neglected, as the majority of the applied pieces are sewn freely and thus have individual characteristics.

Fig. 9: Examples of multi-surface gloves

Special shape gloves

Single-surface gloves

Since around 2015, gloves made from embossed surface material have been increasingly appearing on the European market. These are usually made from a polyester textile base that has been coated with a PU layer on one side. The PU layer in particular is embossed under pressure using heated rollers in a further step. Different patterns can be embossed depending on the surface of the roller. The pattern is repeated on the textile surface after one rotation of the roller. These are usually very fine pattern structures, which leave little scope for identifying gloves with such surface structures. So far, I have been able to distinguish between three types of embossed patterns:

- a. Geometrically identical structure
- b. Geometrically similar structure
- c. Geometrically different (undefined) structure (referring to the entire roller surface)

Embossing errors hardly ever occur during production. The PU surface is very resistant to wear and tear or damage. As with all products cut from sheet material and then sewn into gloves, the seams are also a starting point for identification. However, due to very fine surface structures, direct identification is often difficult (Fig. 10 / 1st image, top row).

Foil gloves

These are disposable gloves made of two polyethylene foils, which are intended for non-clinical use. They are mainly used in the food sector at counters or at European gas stations and have the advantage that they can be pulled on even with wet hands. They are manufactured by layering two PE films and then welding them together in the shape of a hand while simultaneously cutting them apart. However, they play a rather minor role in forensic work, as they are extremely uncomfortable to wear during the commission of a crime and are therefore rarely used.

Chain mail gloves

This special type of glove (also known as stab-proof gloves) originated in the Middle Ages. They consist of hundreds of small, interwoven metal rings (usually stainless steel) and are highly cut and stab resistant. They are among the most effective gloves in this category and are mainly worn today in meat, fish, and shellfish processing, but are also used in certain areas of agriculture and textile and sheet metal processing.

Police gloves

These are protective gloves specially designed for police officers, special forces, customs, and security personnel, combining protection, grip, flexibility, and often tactical features. They are usually made of leather, synthetic materials such as neoprene or nylon, and have Kevlar/aramid inserts and/or polymer coatings. Modern models often offer cut protection, stab protection, knuckle protection, touchscreen capability, and good breathability. *HexArmor* has distinguished itself in the field of needle puncture protection through integrated innovative material layers.

Fighting gloves

This special type of glove includes MMA, kickboxing, Muay Thai, point fighting, Krav Maga, boxing, and sparring gloves. These are padded protective gloves that have been specially developed for striking and combat sports. They are usually made of synthetic or genuine leather with multi-layer foam padding and often breathable mesh inserts. Unlike everyday gloves, they primarily protect the knuckles, back of the hand, and fingers from injuries when striking, while at the same time protecting the opponent.

Diving and water sports gloves

These gloves (also known as wetsuit gloves) are protective gloves made of neoprene (usually 1.5–7 mm thick) that are specially designed for water sports, often with non-slip grip coatings (silicone nubs) on the palm. They protect against cold, cuts, jellyfish, coral, sharp shells, sea urchins, and minor abrasions, while maintaining good tactile sensitivity and mobility. Modern models are often pre-shaped for a better fit, waterproof glued/sewn, and have reinforced palms/fingertips. Smooth neoprene (also called smoothskin, glideskin, superskin, or smooth-skin neoprene) contrasts with porous neoprene (also called mesh neoprene, open-cell, or porous surface). The two types differ mainly in surface structure, thermal performance, wind protection, and durability. Neoprene gloves are also used for other water sports (e.g., windsurfing, surfing, kitesurfing, stand-up paddling, kayaking, water skiing, rafting).

Fig. 10: Exemplary special gloves

Costume gloves

These are actually accessories that are specially made for costumes, parties, theater, cosplay, Halloween, carnival, or LARP. They serve almost exclusively for visual effect and to complete a character's look – protection or functionality are usually irrelevant. They are made of inexpensive materials such as polyester, satin, mesh, faux leather, velvet, latex, stretch fabric, plush/faux fur, metallic foil, glitter, or foam. Lengths range from fingerless to elbow-length and are often embellished with studs, beads, feathers, fur, fringes, ribbons, or LED lights. Some models, such as animal paws or horror gloves, have individual profiles or studs on the inside of the glove.

Erotic gloves

These special gloves, also known as pleasure gloves, are designed specifically for erotic, fetishistic, or sexual scenarios. They are used for visual seduction, sensory stimulation, role-play support, and, in some cases, protection. Materials are usually latex, nitrile, PVC, leather (real or synthetic), satin, mesh/lace, velvet, or textured silicone. They often come in provocative colors (black, red, white, metallic). Many of these gloves emphasize the hands as an erotic tool, including for so-called “solo play.”

This should suffice as an introduction to the world of gloves. Due to the many different types of gloves and materials used, the subject is very broad and much more extensive than the entire field of footwear. Particularly interesting, and not immediately apparent to the layman, are the problems of distinguishing between similar-looking surface patterns on different types of gloves, e.g., between fibrous textile fleece, rough or split leather, foam-like nitrile coatings, and microporous latex coatings. Comparing glove prints alone is a science in itself. But don't be afraid of challenges! No master has ever fallen from sky – as we say in Germany – which means: Nobody is born a master!

The author will publish additional, more in-depth articles on the different types of gloves and the prints they leave, as well as general information related to this topic.

Finally, a few words about the German training of expert candidates.

German training program to become an expert in glove prints

In 2012, the first central expert training course for glove prints took place at the German Federal Criminal Police Office, completing the training area of shoe, tire, and glove prints. In addition to the two-year training program in shoe, tire, and glove prints (including a one-year basic forensic training course in theory and practice covering general crime scene investigation), the curriculum still includes the following specialized modules for the field of glove prints:

Fig. 11: Educational modules for glove print experts, similar to a master's degree program

The first step is to demonstrate the multidimensional nature of a hand and the associated possibilities for leaving prints. Equally important are evaluation options that European dactyloscopists (i.e., experts in fingerprint, palm, and footprint analysis) do not consider during an examination, such as the spacing of finger joints, the proportions of the fingers to the palm, geometries, palm lines, flexion and extension creases, deformations, and skin defects. These distinctive features also provide the expert in technical form traces with indicators for identification or exclusion (see Figs. 12 and 13 for examples). The author will soon publish a separate article on his research findings in this area, as he considers it important to fill a forensic research gap here.

Fig. 12: Different hands

Fig. 13: Different fingers

In addition to glove names and labels, another focus of the training is on the standards and guidelines for gloves that must be considered, which are primarily derived from European and German health protection regulations. A key focus is training on the different types of gloves. This covers the individual manufacturing processes, associated individual characteristics, imprint behavior, and recognizable features in the traces. Occupational safety when handling used gloves also plays a role in the training.

Of course, the options for securing glove prints are just as important for a prospective expert as the evaluation of these prints. During joint discussions of the prints, special features of the prints are discussed, and possible causes of the prints are determined. The classification scheme developed by the author is helpful in this regard; it is also used for database-compatible pattern and model searches. This "Bremen Classification Model" also served as the basis for the glove model database, which was launched in Bremen in 2020 as the first of its kind worldwide and can also be used for image-based identification of clothing.

Fig. 14: Comparison of glove prints (left: crime scene print / right: comparison print taken by a student)

The final focus of the training is comparative work in preparation for writing an expert report in the field of glove prints. Unlike shoe and tire prints, the creation of comparative prints for glove prints is many times more complex and difficult. The main problem is that gloves are usually soft and, moreover, do not contain the perpetrator's hand. Even an expert with small feet can obtain results with a large shoe, as the sole is rigid and the pressure can therefore be distributed across the entire sole. This is not easily possible with a small hand in a large glove, as a finger or similar must be behind the glove material when a glove print is made, otherwise there will be no print.

The glove print module training concludes with the preparation of an expert report within a specified time limit and a final verbal presentation, similar to a court proceeding. The glove prints modules are only one part of the overall training to become a shoe, tire, and glove expert, which is completed with two written and one verbal final exam in the form of an expert presentation before an exam committee.

Prospect

Several training courses and publications have already been organized in Germany. However, this is only a drop in the ocean. Many more events and specialist articles are needed before the topic is fully integrated into the crime scene work of all police forces. My efforts in this field are only a foundation stone, and I ask all my expert colleagues in the fields of shoe and tire prints and dactyloscopy (I have learned that this field is not dealt with by engineers in other countries) to take up the topic of glove prints and develop it further. I am eagerly looking at North America and Southeast Asia, where many forensic universities have been conducting excellent basic research and truly interesting series of experiments in recent years following the PCAST report. It is only through such studies that we can improve and validate our investigation methods and discover new investigative possibilities.

New forensic investigation devices such as the *TrasoScan* and *ToolScan* from the Czech company Laboratory Imaging with the *Lucia Forensic* software, the comparison microscope from the Swiss company Projectina *Vision X*, as well as the Japanese digital microscope *Keyence VHX-X1*, enable us to carry out increasingly detailed and in-depth investigations in the field of technical form traces. My appeal is directed in particular to our young forensic students, who will one day follow in the footsteps of Gross, Abbott, Bodziak, Carlsson, Cassidy, Davis, Hamm, Hara, Katterwe, Keereweer, Majamaa, Mikkonen, Shor, Wiesner, Wu, and Ytti: As part of your forensic training, be sure to conduct basic research on glove prints! Broaden your horizons and try to incorporate new research findings from other disciplines into your investigations. Then share your knowledge with your crime scene investigation units and police response teams and encourage them to secure the traces and the gloves that left the prints. That would be the best foundation for successful forensic work.

Literature

- **Braune, M.** PPT ‚Schuh-, Reifen- und Handschuhspuren (Shoe, tire, and glove prints)‘, *Hochschule für Öffentliche Verwaltung Bremen / Landeskriminalamt Bremen*. Bremen/Germany 2002.
- **Braune, M.** ‚Studienunterlagen zum Sachverständigen für Handschuhspuren (Study materials for glove print examiners)‘, *Sachverständigenausbildung beim Bundeskriminalamt*. Wiesbaden/Germany 2012.
- **Braune, M.** PPT ‚Handschuhspuren - Ein Überblick über die Möglichkeiten (Gloveprints - An overview of the possibilities)‘, *Kriminaltechnisches Symposium für Werkzeug- und sonstige Formspuren*. Potsdam/Germany 2015.
- **Braune, M.** ‚Fortbildung Handschuhspuren für Sachverständige (Advanced training in glove prints for senior experts)‘, *Handschuh-Workshop für Technische Formspuren des LKA Niedersachsen und LKA Bremen*, Lüneburg/Germany 2016.
- **Braune, M.** ‚Handschuhspuren Teil 1 (gloveprints - anatomical influences, textile gloves Vol. 1)‘, *Die Kriminalpolizei*. Hilden/Germany 2016; (4) 31-32.
- **Braune, M.** ‚Handschuhspuren Teil 2 (gloveprints - leather, dipping forms, dipped textiles, nubs, foils and multi-surface gloves Vol. 2)‘, *Die Kriminalpolizei*. Hilden/Germany 2017; (1) 29-31.
- **Braune, M.** ‚Handschuhspuren (gloveprints - evaluability, searching for and securing evidence and examination)‘, *Der rote Faden - Grundsätze der Kriminalpraxis. Kriminalistik Verlag*. Heidelberg/Germany 2022; 422-425.
- **Jordan, H. and Fritz, H.** ‚Lederhandschuh-Abdruckspuren - Darstellung, Sicherung und Experimentalspur (Leather glove prints - representation, trace evidence and experimental trace)‘, *Forum der Kriminalistik*. Berlin/Germany, 1970; (8) 378-379.
- **Lambourne, G.** ‚Glove print identification‘, *Journal of Forensic Identification*, USA 1988. Vol. 38, (1) 7-24.
- **Marquardt, W., Kurras, G. and Schill, R.** (1987) ‚Materielle Beweismittel - Handschuhspuren (Material evidence - gloveprints)‘. *Ministerium des Inneren*. Berlin/Germany 1987; 240-253
- **Santamaria Beltran, F.** ‚Traces of Gloves‘, *International Criminal Police Review*, 1952 (56) 79-81.
- **Sommer.** ‚Verbrecher mit Handschuhen (Criminal with gloves)‘, *Die Polizei - Zeitschrift für das gesamte Polizeiwesen im Deutschen Reich*, Carl Heymanns Verlag, Berlin/Germany 1925
- **Svensson, A. and Wendel, O.** (1956) ‚Tatortuntersuchung - Moderne Methoden der Verbrechensaufklärung - Handschuhspuren (Crime Detection - modern methods of criminal investigation - gloveprints)‘. *Schmidt-Römhild Verlag*, Lübeck/Germany 1956; 45-49.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project was supported by funding from the Forensic Expert Office Braune and created in collaboration with the Criminal Investigation Department of the State Criminal Police Office of Bremen, Germany. The opinions, findings, conclusions, or recommendations expressed in this publication/program/exhibition are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect those of the State Criminal Police Office of Bremen.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Matthias Braune: Concept design; data curation; formal analysis; funding acquisition; investigation; methodology; project management; resources; supervision; visualization; writing the original draft and revising and editing the draft; validation

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author of this manuscript confirms that he has no connections to or interests in organizations or institutions that have financial or non-financial interests in the topics or materials covered in this manuscript. This is an informational transfer of scientific content from experts to experts.

STATEMENT ON DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

ORCID

Matthias Braune <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-0219-4838>

How to cite this article: Braune, M. German basic research, classification, and training in glove prints. In *Forensic Eng.* (Vol. 2026, Number 2, pp. 1–18). MB Art & Publishing Weyhe-Germany. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19581499>